
Performance of Maharashtra in India's Export of Agriculture Commodities

Dr. Sangramsing Vijayram Nalawade

Associate Professor

Amdar Shashikant Shinde Mahavidyalay, Medha

Corresponding Author – Dr. Sangramsing Vijayram Nalawade

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Abstract:

Agriculture trade has been playing vital role in achieving economic growth and alleviating poverty for developing countries like India. Figures from last several years describes India's agriculture export is continuously increasing and the country has developed export competitiveness also. India's agricultural export touched the highest ever level of US\$50.21 billion in the year 2021-22. Considering these, the present study examined the performance of Maharashtra in comparison with India's export of agriculture commodities. In the present study Maharashtra's export of major fruits and vegetables in comparison with India is analysed. Study revealed that in the year 2021-22 India's revenue through fruit export was Rs. 4903 crore in which Maharashtra's share was Rs. 3714 crore. Maharashtra's fruit export of Mango, Grapes and Orange has been playing crucial role in the fruit export of India, in the year 2021-22 Maharashtra's revenue in India's revenue of Mango, Grapes and Orange export was 86.54%, 82.10% and 94.08% respectively.

Keywords: *Agriculture, Export, Commodity, Fruits.*

Introduction:

Agriculture is the main occupation of majority Indians and also major economic factor of India. The role of agriculture growth in uplifting income level of rural people is inherent in country like India. The country has increased agriculture production and become self-sufficiency in the majority of the crops. India has historical background of export of spices and cotton. India's vast production base of agriculture products offers big opportunities for export. India is the largest producer as well as largest exporter of cereal products in the world. Rice occupies the major share in India's total cereals export. Maharashtra is in the top positions in production of Cereals, pulses, oil seeds, dairy products, fisheries and animal products and also leading state in the India for export of agriculture produce. Maharashtra stood first in the export of horticulture crops of country which includes

fruits like grapes, banana, orange etc. and in many vegetables also.

Objectives:

The study focuses on examining the trends and growth of fruits and vegetables exports of the India and Maharashtra.

Scope of the Study:

The present study focuses on comparative analysis of India and Maharashtra's Fruits and vegetables export during the year 2019-20 to 2021-22.

Research Methodology:

This research paper is descriptive in nature. This study is mainly based on secondary data. The data required for such study has been collected from secondary sources such as books, journals, articles, research papers and internet.

Review of Literature:

Bhatia, J.K. (2021) explores the growth and output of agricultural exports from India during the period 2000-2019. It is revealed that Indian agricultural exports have increased, but the proportion of agricultural exports to the country's overall exports has decreased. Study concluded that Indian agriculture export will be more in the future, particularly rice and spices. C Paramasivan, & R Pasupathi (2017) analyzed the status of agro based food products and its exports performance of India. ResearcherS. explore that Agro based industries are playing important role and increases employment to the farmers, agricultural workers, wholesalers, retailers, exporters, Malini L Tantri (2021) provides a detailed analysis of the trends and characteristics of agricultural exports in India and also critically evaluates the trajectories of agriculture policy making in India. Vinod Kumar (2021) in his research analyse the trends and performance of agricultural trade during 1990-91 to 2020-21. He explore that the largest markets for India's agricultural products are USA, China, Bangladesh, UAE, Vietnam, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Nepal, Iran and Malaysia. The study also revealed that share of agricultural exports to agricultural gross value added (GVA) increased 4.6 per cent from 1990-91 to 2020-21.

Agricultural Export of India:

India has historical background of export. Historically, spices and cotton goods have been exported from India to the rest of the world. But in recent years India's export is not limited to spices and cotton only. Now days, India supplies many agricultural commodities, such as tea, coffee, rice, cashew, oil meals, fruits, vegetables, meat in international markets. Over the years, India has developed export competitiveness in certain specialised products (ITA, 2021). In terms of global agriculture production, India stands second, whereas with 2.2 per cent share in global exports, it ranks in the eighth position (WTO, 2019). Recent figures explore that, India is among the top ten exporters of agricultural products in the world. The Agriculture Export Policy (AEP) 2018 of the Government of India (GoI), aims at achieving an export target of US\$ 60 billion by 2022 and US\$ 100 billion within a few years, thereafter. In actual, during the financial year 2021-22, India's agricultural export touched the highest ever level of US\$50.21 billion even under global crisis of Covid; this is indeed great achievement even under such critical condition. As per provisional data realised by department of commerce India's total agricultural export were US\$53.15 billion during the financial year 2022-23.

Table No. 1: Fruits Export of Maharashtra and India

Sr. No.	Commodity	Export	2021-22		2020-21		2019-20	
			Quantity (MT)	Value (Crore)	Quantity (MT)	Value (Crore)	Quantity (MT)	Value (Crore)
1	Mango	Maharashtra	20,874	283	19,184	241	29,884	307
		India	27,873	327	21,034	272	49,657	400
2	Grapes	Maharashtra	1,65,245	1,890	1,79,126	2,034	1,53,693	2,019
		India	2,63,076	2,302	2,46,107	2,298	1,93,690	2,177
3	Banana	Maharashtra	2,73,381	923	1,63,696	556	1,08,961	429
		India	3,76,572	1,179	2,32,518	740	1,95,746	659
4	Orange	Maharashtra	1,07,826	382	1,46,565	424	84,353	230
		India	1,19,548	406	1,62,540	454	93,879	254
5	Pomegranate	Maharashtra	16,381	236	17,724	224	32,137	408
		India	99,043	689	67,977	517	80,548	688

(Source: Commissionerate of Agriculture, GoM)

Table No. 1 shows details of five major fruit exports from Maharashtra and India during 2019–20 to 2021–22. Data shows that grapes occupy number one in total fruit exports of India and Maharashtra as well. It shows that grape exports from India have increased constantly, but there are ups and downs in Maharashtra's grape exports. In 2019–20, Maharashtra's share in India's grape exports was 92.74%, which decreased up to 82.10% in 2021–22. In the fruit exports of India and Maharashtra, banana and orange are the two most important fruits after grapes. Data shows that in 2021–22, Maharashtra's average

share in total fruit exports of India was 75.05%. Considering Maharashtra's share in India's fruits export in the year 2021-22 mangos have 86.54% share, grapes have 82.10% share, bananas have 78.28% share, oranges have 94.08% share, and pomegranates have 34.25% share. It shows that among all fruits exported by India in 2021–22, Maharashtra's share in orange exports is very high (94.08%), whereas pomegranates occupy a low share (34.25%). Comparing Maharashtra's fruits export during the study period, banana is the only fruit that shows continuous increasing trend.

Chart No. 1 Fruits Export of Maharashtra and India

Above chart No.1 indicates that India's grapes export increased from Rs. 2177 crore in 2019-20 to Rs. 2302 crore in 2021-22; on the other hand, Maharashtra's grape export decreased from Rs. 2019 crore in 2019-20 to Rs. 1890 crore in 2021-22. Considering the total revenue generated through fruit exports by Maharashtra (Rs. 3714 crore) in 2021–22, grapes contributed 50.88% of the total revenue, followed by bananas at 24.85%, oranges at 10.28%, mangoes at 7.61%, and pomegranates at 6.35%. Data shows that, in 2021–22, India

generated Rs. 4903 crore through fruit exports, of which Maharashtra's share was Rs. 3714 (75.73%). Out of India's total fruit export (Rs. 4903 crore) in 2021–22, Maharashtra's grape export was Rs. 1890 crore (38.54%), followed by bananas at Rs. 923 (18.82%) crore, oranges at Rs. 382 crore (7.79%), mangoes at Rs. 283 (7.61%) crore, and pomegranates at Rs. 236 crore (6.35%). Grapes contributed 46.95% of India's total fruit export in 2021–22, and on the other hand, Maharashtra's revenue was 82.10% of India's total grapes export in 2021–22.

Table No. 2 Vegetables Export by Maharashtra and India

Sr. No.	Commodity	Export	2021-22		2020-21		2019-20	
			Quantity (MT)	Value (Crore)	Quantity (MT)	Value (Crore)	Quantity (MT)	Value (Crore)
1	Onion	Maharashtra	5,78,473	1,400	7,96,898	1,515	7,29,563	1,350
		India	15,36,905	3,431	15,75,923	2,822	11,48,924	2,319
2	Other Vegetables (Other than Onion)	Maharashtra	1,09,242	607	1,12,363	655	1,31,023	669
		India	7,70,233	2,161	6,82,086	2,143	7,54,007	2,065

(Source: Commissionerate of Agriculture, GoM)

Table No. 2 shows export of onion and other vegetables of Maharashtra and India from 2019-20 to 2021-22. Data shows that Maharashtra's share in onion export of India was 58.23% in the year 2019-20, which decreased up to 53.68% in the next year and it further decreased up to 40.80% in the year 2021-22. Above table explore that the Maharashtra's share in vegetables (Other than Onion) export was 32.39% in the year

2019-20 which decreased up to 31.03% in the next year and it further decreased up to 28.08% in the year 2021-22. Data shows that onion export of Maharashtra and India was increased after 2019-20 but it decreased after 2020-21. Figures showed that Maharashtra's export of other vegetables has been continuously decreased during the three years of study period. (C)

Chart No. 2 Vegetables Export by Maharashtra and India

Above chart shows vegetable export of India was Rs. 4384 crore in the year 2019-20. It showed a continuously increasing trend and reached up to Rs. 5592 crore in 2021-22. But considering vegetable export of Maharashtra, it was Rs. 2019 crore in 2019-20 which decreased up to Rs. 2017 in 2021-22.

Findings:

1. Maharashtra has been playing crucial role in fruit export of India.
2. Mangos, Grapes and Mango are the three important fruits of Maharashtra which also share major part of fruits export of India.
3. In the year 2019-20 Maharashtra's share was 81.21% of India's total fruits export, which decreased up to 75.74% in 2021-22.

4. India's fruits export is increased by 17.35% from the year 2019-20 to 2021-22 whereas Maharashtra's fruits export is increased by 9.46% in the same period.
5. During 2019-20 to 2021-22 Maharashtra's share in India's onion export was decreased by 17.41% and other vegetables decreased by 4.31%.
6. In the year 2021-22 India generated Rs. 4903 crore through fruit export out of which Maharashtra's share was Rs. 3714 crore.
7. Maharashtra's fruit export of Mango, Grapes and Orange has been playing crucial role in the fruit export of India, in the year 2021-22 Maharashtra's revenue in India's revenue of Mango, Grapes and Orange export was 86.54%, 82.10% and 94.08% respectively.

Conclusion:

Over the years, Indian agricultural products have come to hold a crucial role in the global market, this exhibit that agriculture production also play vital role in earning foreign currency for India. There are several agriculture commodities which got key export spot in India's overall export. Study reveals that Maharashtra has been playing crucial role in fruit export of India. In the year 2021-22 Maharashtra's share in fruit export of India was 75.74 percent, it indicates that among all states of India Maharashtra is leading state in agriculture export. Mangos and Grapes are the two important fruits of Maharashtra which occupy major share in agriculture export of India. India as well as Maharashtra's fruits export has been increases over the period.

References:

1. Accelerating Maharashtra's Export Competitiveness, document accessed by, <https://wtcmumbai.org/pdf/report->

- [presentiton/2018/Maharashtra-RESEARCH-STUDY-23feb2018.pdf](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320465482_A_study_on_growth_and_performance_of_Indian_agro_base_d_exports)
2. Agriculture Export policy of Maharashtra, document accessed by <https://www.msamb.com/Documents/bc513f39-b929-4e4b-9a2b-98e2b914a5a3.pdf>
3. Bhatia, J.K., Mehta, V.P., Bhardwaj, N. and Nimbrayan, P.K. (2021). Export-Import Performance of Major Agricultural Commodities in India. *Economic AffairS.*, **66**(1): 117-126.
4. C Paramasivan, & R Pasupathi (2017) A Study on Growth and Performance of Indian Agro based exports, International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research document accessed by, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320465482_A_study_on_growth_and_performance_of_Indian_agro_base_d_exports
5. Economic Survey of Maharashtra 2022-23, 2021-22, 2020-21, 2019-20
6. India's agriculture and food export Opportunities and challenges document accessed by <https://www.nabard.org/auth/writereaddata/tender/2501231533indias-agriculture-and-food-exports.pdf>
7. Malini L Tantri (2021) Policy and performance of Agriculture Export of India, ISEC Working Paper No. 509 document, accessed by, <http://www.isec.ac.in/WP%20509%20-%20Malini%20L%20T%20-%20Final.pdf>
8. Vinod Kumar (2021) Trends and Performance of India's Agricultural Trade in the Midst of COVID-19 Pandemic, Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics Volume 76, Number 3, July-September 2021

Websites:

1. <https://krishi.maharashtra.gov.in/>
2. <https://commerce.gov.in/>
3. <https://www.pib.gov.in>